

Management

MOBILE SUBSCRIBERS' SATISFACTION TOWARDS SERVICE QUALITY IN TUTICORIN DIST

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ABSTRACT

Due to huge competition in the service sector, service providers have to focus on lots of aspects in connection with satisfying the customer. Especially, the providers need to focus on increasing the service quality to maintain their position in the competitive market. Subscribers' satisfaction is one of the determinants of service quality and perception carried by subscribers plays an important role in choosing a mobile service provider. This paper presents a service quality analysis of mobile subscribers in Tuticorin Dist.

Keywords:

Subscribers, Service, Quality, Market, VAS & Mobile.

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1. INTRODUCTION

As today's market is customer oriented, quality is the indication of success and survival of a product or service. These days, service quality has become an important research topic in view of its significant relationship to cost, profitability, customer satisfaction, customer retention, service guarantees and financial performance. Quality is the real advertisement for every service and goods. Without quality the future of the company will be questionable. The service sector is expanding at an increasing rate and is becoming intensely competitive (Chen, et.al., 1994; Johnson, et.al., 1988). As such, service quality has become a very important issue in marketing and has received much attention due to being deregulated and thus has increased the competition among service providers (e.g.: health care, banking and telecommunications in the 1980's and utilities in the 1990's). Service quality has become so important that some businesses, not only need high levels of service quality for success, but in some cases, need it for survival.

2. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To assess the factors determining the choices of a service providers.
- To study the subscribers' attitude towards providers services.

- To identify the problems those are being faced by the subscribers.
- To offer suggestions to overcome the problems.

3. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

“The greatest satisfaction is depending upon the quality of the service. Quality is the state of complete positive and favourable thoughts towards the given service. Good quality is one of the most crucial components of retaining the subscribers. Every subscriber possesses the right to get proper and standard service. Over the last decades, quality is decreasing for everyday. There are a number of service providers and there is severe competition among these service providers. It is in the context the study has been undertaken, to find out the service quality in mobile communication service providers in Tuticorin Dist.

4. SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The scope of the study is confined to the service quality in service providers in Tuticorin District. In Tuticorin District there are good numbers of mobile subscribers in both urban and rural areas, having advanced technology communication equipment. Both the government and private service providers have been included in this study. Further, the study is confined to factors that influence the subscribers to select a particular service operator and the subscribers’ attitudes towards various mobile service providers. As regards subscribers’ attitude towards quality, the study is confined to the problems that are faced by them in availing mobile communication services.

5. ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

LEVEL OF SATISFACTION ON SERVICE QUALITY

The service quality has a significant role in satisfying the consumers. The quality determines the product or services to withstand in the market for a longer course of time. Thus, the future of the service provider entirely depends on the quality of the service rendered by the mobile communication service provider. Therefore, the researcher has analysed the satisfaction of the respondents regarding service quality.

Table 1: Level of satisfaction on service quality

Service Quality			HDS	DS	N	S	HS	Total
Quality of SMS	Public sector	Count	4	30	46	16	8	104
		% within	3.8	28.8	44.2	15.4	7.7	100
	Private sector	Count	26	141	232	93	130	622
		% within	4.2	22.7	37.3	15.0	20.9	100
Quality of value added service	Public sector	Count	2	1	15	71	15	104
		% within	1.9	1.0	14.4	68.3	14.4	100
	Private sector	Count	6	29	247	256	84	622
		% within	1.0	4.7	39.7	41.2	13.5	100
Clarity of signal and	Public sector	Count	6	31	51	15	1	104
		% within	5.8	29.8	49.0	14.4	1.0	100

connection	Private sector	Count	44	65	156	291	66	622
		% within	7.1	10.5	25.1	46.8	10.6	100
Quality of Internet	Public sector	Count	1	2	26	61	14	104
		% within	1.0	1.9	25.0	58.7	13.5	100
	Private sector	Count	31	50	113	309	119	622
		% within	5.0	8.0	18.2	49.7	19.1	100

Source: Computed Primary Data

The above table shows that

a) Quality of SMS: In the public sector, 44.2 per cent of the respondents are neutral, 28.8 percent of the respondents are dissatisfied, 15.4 percent of the respondents are satisfied, 7.7 percent of the respondents are highly satisfied and 3.8 per cent of the respondents are highly dissatisfied with the quality of SMS. In the private sector, 37.3 per cent of the respondents are neutral, 22.7 percent of the respondents are dissatisfied, 20.9 percent of the respondents are highly satisfied, 15 percent of the respondents are satisfied and 4.2 per cent of the respondents are highly dissatisfied with the quality of SMS.

It is inferred that 44.2 per cent of the public sector respondents are neutral and 37.3 per cent of the private sector respondents are neutral with quality of SMS.

b) Quality of value added services: In the public sector, 68.3 per cent of the respondents are satisfied, 14.4 percent of the respondents are highly satisfied, 14.4 percent of the respondents are neutral, 1.9 percent of the respondents are highly dissatisfied and 1.0 per cent of the respondent is dissatisfied with the quality of value added service. In the private sector, 41.2 per cent of the respondents are satisfied, 39.7 percent of the respondents are neutral, 13.5 percent of the respondents are highly satisfied, 4.7 percent of the respondents are dissatisfied and only one per cent of the respondents are highly dissatisfied with quality of value added service.

It is inferred that 68.3 per cent of the public sector respondents are satisfied and 41.2 per cent of the private sector respondents are satisfied with the quality of the value added service.

c) Clarity of signal and connection: In the public sector, 49 per cent of the respondents are neutral, 29.8 percent of the respondents are dissatisfied, 14.4 percent of the respondents are satisfied, 5.8 percent of the respondents are highly dissatisfied and only one per cent of the respondents are highly satisfied with the clarity of signal and connection. In the private sector, 46.8 per cent of the respondents are satisfied, 25.1 percent of the respondents are neutral, 10.6 percent of the respondents are highly satisfied, 10.5 percent of the respondents are dissatisfied and 7.1 percent of the respondents are highly dissatisfied with the clarity of signal and connection.

It is inferred that 49 per cent of the public sector respondents are neutral and 46.8 per cent of the private sector respondents are satisfied with the clarity of signal and connection.

d) The quality of internet: In the public sector, 58.7 per cent of the respondents are satisfied, 25 percent of the respondents are neutral, 13.5 percent of the respondents are highly satisfied, 1.9

percent of the respondents are dissatisfied and only one per cent of the respondents are highly dissatisfied with quality of internet. In the private sector, 49.7 per cent of the respondents are satisfied, 19.1 percent of the respondents are highly satisfied, 18.2 percent of the respondents are neutral 8 per cent of the respondents are dissatisfied and 5.0 percent of the respondents are highly dissatisfied with quality of internet.

It is inferred that 58.7 per cent of the public sector respondents are satisfied and 49.7 per cent of the private sector respondents are satisfied with quality of internet.

Ranking on factors Influencing satisfaction towards service quality

Table 2: Ranking on factors Influencing satisfaction towards service quality

Service Quality	Public Sector		Private Sector	
	Mean Score	Rank	Mean Score	Rank
Quality of SMS	2.94	III	2.29	IV
Quality of value added service	3.77	II	3.61	II
Clarity of signal and connection	2.88	IV	3.43	III
Quality of internet	3.81	I	3.69	I

Source: Computed Primary Data

From the above table it is clear that in the public sector, quality of the internet has the first rank followed by quality of value added services, quality of SMS and clarity of signal and connection, whereas in private sector quality of the internet has the first rank followed by quality of value added services, clarity of signal and connection and quality of SMS.

In both sectors, quality of the internet is mostly influenced in the satisfaction of the respondents.

6. FINDINGS

- 44.2 per cent of the public sector respondents are neutral and 37.3 per cent of the private sector respondents are neutral with quality of SMS.
- 68.3 per cent of the public sector respondents are satisfied and 41.2 per cent of the private sector respondents are satisfied with the quality of the value added service.
- 49 per cent of the public sector respondents are neutral and 46.8 per cent of the private sector respondents are satisfied with the clarity of signal and connection.
- 58.7 per cent of the public sector respondents are satisfied and 49.7 per cent of the private sector respondents are satisfied with quality of internet.
- In Both sectors, among all factors, quality of the internet is mostly influenced in the satisfaction of the respondents.

7. CONCLUSION

Thus, it concludes that service quality occupies the major role in subscribers' satisfaction. It the critical task to each and every operator to provide quality service to their subscribers in mobile communication. Quality will increase the quantity of the mobile subscribers. So the mobile subscribers have to concentrate on SMS service because it is in the neutral stage and they have to

strengthen the following area i.e. value added service, signal & connection and internet. If the operator provides better service, then the subscribers will be satisfied. If the subscribers are satisfied, then they will continually have service. Thus, the operators can have their subscribers for the upcoming periods.

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